

ISSN 0975 - 6302

TERESIAN JOURNAL OF ENGLISH STUDIES

January - March
2022
Volume XIV
Issue I

Double-blind
Peer Reviewed
International
Quarterly

Listed in:

- § ProQuest
- § International Scientific Indexing (ISI)
- § ResearchBib (Academic Resource Index)
- § International Institute of Organized Research (I2OR)
- § J-Gate
- § Ulrichsweb & Ulrich's Periodicals Directory

"Historiopoetics: The Frame of Narration in Easterine Kire's *Mari*"

Ramesh Sharma*

Abstract

North-East India has seldom got enough attention from modern narration to explore its intellectual potentialities in spite of its rich intellectual tradition since the days of the epic *Mahabharata*. Conflicts are the new orders of the world today, yet understanding of them in this region is something different, that it has often been seen as if a stellar catastrophe, a security threat, hitting hard to every other human possibilities. However this is only a telescopic view from its defective lenses. The conflict thus (mis)understood one dimensional which is rather a politics of (mis)narration; the other side has always been eclipsed. I contend to say that the same supposed conflict has been understood by some potential writers as coming into new consciousness, new possibilities, and an enabling phenomenon, in which Easterine Kire is quite vocal. In Kire's fiction *Mari*, as this paper wants to maintain, she has been able to demonstrate that the intellectual fecundity of the region, representatively Nagaland, can be tapped only through a different type of narration, consciously termed here as historiopetics, in which both the conflicting history and interpretations sustain in a dynamic of relationship often embedded in each other.

Keywords: *Technical Terms: History, Narration, Conflict, and Representation.*

*Ramesh Sharma, Assistant Professor (Senior), Department of English, School of Humanities and Social Sciences, Assam Don Bosco University, Tapesia Campus, Guwahati -782402, Assam, India,
Email: sharma02021975@gmail.com

What happens in the modern history is a rupture in its faithful exploration and representation of the North-East India as it has been often labeled as “conflict” zone, a no-go zone. Stigmatized as such that even the Ministry of Home Affairs, Government of India, North East Division, has to jump to the conclusion that the “... historical factors such as language/ethnicity, tribal rivalry, migration, control over local resources ... have resulted in a fragile security situation in the North Eastern States. This has resulted in violence and diverse demands by various Indian Insurgent Groups” (www.mha.gov.in, accessed date 30-0-2020). The observation has its own rationality and must have come from the quite long experience in the region and yet to regard it in totality will be a hasty generalization. What is evidenced in the observation is that the entire region is given a threat identity, which can not be justified. The term “fragile security” as a representative term provides the point that this paper tries to confront, deviate from and explore other peculiarities of the region. I contend to say this representatively misleading image is gradually evaporating in the recent times with the emergence of some of the vocal intellectuals who have an inbuilt narrative technique in their representation of the region that can delineate other enabling possibilities.

A moral discomfiture from the narrative of “conflict” rendering has already been felt. As Prajana Parimita Ray contends, “Given the cultural plurality of Northeast India, it would be an act of interpretive fallacy if the critics and scholars view the literature from this region only through the narrow prism of terror or violence” (Ray 57). Similarly, showing discontentment to the narrative of conflict, Shiva Prasad Sharma, in reference to Nagaland, points to other imperatives to understand the region. He writes, “Nagaland ... does not have a pleasant temporal framework to re-

late. Its present as well as past is fraught with deep scars of conflict ... Yet, in the midst of violence, there is a thriving diversity of people with diverse cultural Nagaland apart from being a space marred by conflict is also a storehouse of life stories. It is a tapestry where myth, legends, stories conglomerate with lived realities of a people” (Sharma 10801).

Historically, the North East India has its own contribution in intellectual tradition, for instance making of the greatest world epics, *Mahabharata* for instance, that recounts the rise and fall of the Kuru dynasty. Chitrangadha and Hidimma, two of the characters in the epic from the region, have played their role in the fabric of the epic. In other words, this being an example, the North East has been potentially linked to one of the greatest of the intellectual traditions since ancient times. The region also has an intellectual history beside the subject matter of the modern history to be understood and accepted and the same has been reflecting as a legacy in some of the writings that emerge from the region. Reading a text from the region in the line of the intellectual tradition, *Mahabharata* for instance, as this writing does, tends to suggest an odd combination given the dimension of the subject matter they cover; the latter covers the entire Indian sub-continent but the former Nagaland and its bitter experience with the invaders-Japanese and British is a novel and the other one is an epic. However, the oddity being an instance we can see how the small text like *Mari* by Easterine Kire can initiate and testify, like the latter, a big narrative of the region.

Easterine Kire and other being Mamang Dai, Mitra Phukan and Temsula Ao have been constantly trying to rethink the epistemologically of the region making the “tapestry” the area of aesthetic experience and aligning it with the rich intellectual tradition. Their writings do not make

the narrative of conflict and insecurity as the arrival. Rather they accept them in as much as the beginning and through them spiral into the yet unfolded centres of rich intellectual resources. However, in this paper I will limit my argument in terms of Easterine Kire, as an example, because with the achieved content of the text, through the themes of conflict and insecurity, she has clearly penetrated the literary dimension to rejuvenate the fecund narrative of the region drawing from the tapestry-local history, myth and spirituality which otherwise is a rare phenomenon in the representation of the region. In terms of the use of the subject matter, as this essay contends, *Mari* aligns itself into the tradition of the epic and hence it is potentially seminal in building a historical perspective for the region. It can be seen that in *Mari* history and literature intersect with each other and in this historicization of the text and textualization of the history, the history of the region *only* as a grand-narrative collapses, suggests its inadequacy and underlines an imperative to understand it as a metaphor. At the same time the fiction ceases to be only a fantasy; it is not purely poetic rather but is also equally raw and naked. In other words, the identity of the region that the fiction covers is neither totally historic nor poetics. It should emerge, as can be elaborated next, from a technique of narration, representation, which can be framed as historiopoetics.

But then, how does the historiopoetics work? The historiopoetics does not totally reject the claim of the linear history, nor the literary. Although it is aware of their inadequacy in representation, it uses both. In it sometimes history and poetry operate distinctively as much as they can so as not to dilute their identity. But only if they fail in representation, they draw from the other. This has been brilliantly demonstrated by *Mari*. About the technique of narration in *Mari* Kire says "I wrote it in my head" at first before penning it

down. What she wrote in her head is something that goes beyond both the poetic and historical dimensions. In one of my recent interactions with the writer in reference to a web-talk programme organized by the Department of English, School of Humanities and Social Sciences, Assam Don Bosco University, Kire thus summarizes her focus which is imperative: "It's important for younger generations to read their own local history and have a sense of pride in who their ancestors were so that they will not have to accept stereotypes about their culture, their history, their identities." Kire is underlining an imperative history that can be generated through writing, as in *Mari* and other texts from her, in which the generation can have a "sense of pride." Why the writer feels the necessity of this imperative once again reminds us of the generalized stigma, a "stereotype" triggered by the modern history that pathetically eclipsed the intellectual potentiality of the region for the generation which compelled it to believe in the stereotype promoting it even through the statutory agencies.

The situation certainly strikes every thinking individual who is aware of the cerebral potentiality of the region behind the stigma but only a few like Easterine Kire dares to confront the stigma rendering it no more than inadequate. What predominantly figures in Kire's *Mari* is the textuality of history and historicity of text, the history also becomes a fiction and the fiction transgressing its fantastic border more resourceful and alive. Apparently the Anglo-Japanese war 1944 at Kohima is the history that goes into the fabric of the fiction unfolding a series of pages of memory as the resource unlike only the factual evidence the linear history generally considers. Kire writes in her notes to *Mari* how the text unfolds:

I started writing *Mari* when I was about sixteen. I wrote it in my head during my summer holidays with *Mari* in northern Assam, listening to

her tell this story and badgering her to tell it again and again. I always knew I would write it down one day. I finally wrote it in 2003, with the help of Mari and a diary she had kept during the war years... I must have read the diary a hundred times and still I cry a little at certain parts (Author's note to *Mari*).

It was the diary then handed over to her by Khrielievü Mari O'Leary, the eldest sister of her mother and the oral stories that she narrated to Kire speak between the lines in the fiction. In other words, the nature and function of the memory in *Mari* is very significant. The undiluted 1944 war, the linear history, the real war between Japanese and English and its ramification in the Nagas which otherwise is not their war becomes alive in the fiction though through the agency of memory. Until this point, the history operates under its own capacity.

But for Kire the war in reference is not simply a historical incident; it has a cosmic dimension and for its representation, since the linear history has its limitation, she has to take a refuge in poetics. In the same note to *Mari* she thus adds "I was left with the impression that the war, for us, was almost equivalent to the big bang, the beginning of all life." On the other hand, the text of *Mari* is incomplete without the timeline, those facts of the 1944 in which the Japanese army clashed with the British which unfortunately made the local, the Nagas, refugees in their own land which was an unprecedented experience, a cosmic tragedy for the locals. In other words history and fiction often look for each other in Kire and in this communication the fiction of *Mari* flowers. The impact of the war goes beyond the apparent aftermath of any such catastrophic war and extends up to human psychology which is evidenced by the diary that Kire refers to in her note from which she primarily draws the resource of the fiction. In this sense the fiction is also inter-

textuality between the two memories before it flows into its actual stream. This drawing from memory, making memory as the primary archive of the resource (nevertheless, Kire has also claimed in the talk in reference she verifies the anecdotes from factual references) is something that distinguishes Kire from the other writers in the region which further senses another unique tradition of the region towards which I will shift in a while. But what the diary unfolds to impregnate the fiction with a structural significance needs an attention here first.

The structure of the content that flows from the memory informs us that *Mari* is apparently a story of a 17 years young Naga girl engulfed by the catastrophic battle. According to a reviewer Lois A Gomez, in the text "A young Naga woman sees her world collapse when her foreigner fiancée dies during the battle of Kohima and embraces her life and circumstances...Kire narrates in *Mari* (2010) her aunt's life, love and passion. The novella is a literary souvenir of the once little town that became the grave of the Japanese imperial dreams" (Gomez 1). The war forced people to disperse leaving their home behind in which the family of Mari is not an exception. In this sense the story of Mari is also representative. Mari and her younger sisters are separated and she has to take care of her younger sisters. As the war continues, she has to move from one hideout, the cattle shed, to other to escape the onslaught of the Japanese soldiers. Tired and hungry they are forced to feed on herbs in the forest.

Throughout this ordeal of life, Mari is haunted by the memory of her British fiancé Vic, a soldier, who was shot by a Japanese sniper in the battle of Kohima. Mari and her sister's return to Kohima a day before the Japanese are defeated to find the total destruction of their village by shelling from artillery. They can see only three

wooden pillars of their house standing. The Deputy Commissioner suggests clearing of the debris to give the village a new form but the villagers do not like the idea as it might destroy the traditional boundaries of their clans which might further spiral into community fights. The administration eventually concedes and the villagers are given timbers and material to rebuild their houses in their own way. They clear the debris and grieve and mourn for their slaughtered kins. However, more grieving is discouraged as they think that it will anger the spirits, their ancestors, which is a belief in Angami communities to salvage life after a catastrophe. As the spring returns, symbolically the nature rebuilds itself and the village with green grass, leaves and flowers. Eventually Mari goes to Chandigarh to be trained as nurse. Thus the fiction begins with a catastrophe and ends with nature rejuvenating it.

To recall the unique tradition that I referred to we need to re-capture three reverberations from the story. The structure of the story reverberates with three significances in general: 1) it carries the tragedy of Mari, the end of her unrequited love story, "a tale of romance in times of war" as a review claims in "Hindustan Times" dated Jan 01, 2011 claims; 2) it concedes to and gratifies the sentiments of the villagers, their community feeling to avoid clashes and their local spirituality; and 3) it eventually returns to nature which is both symbolic as rejuvenation and a part of the life of Angami people. The first can be read as an emotional story, a catastrophe of the war, which however is a common theme in every fiction. But throughout her odyssey it is the memory of Vic, the memory in working drives her between the edges of her situation and reality. Thus the tragic history of Mari gets reinforced through the agency of the memory.

With the gratification of the sentiments of the villagers and nature, the fiction enters into another level of the local history. And this history

confronts the linear history, the war, with its humane, binding and enabling nature. By local history I mean local belief, myth, folktales, spirituality, community feelings and nature association that culminate the narrative, which mark a distinct identity of the Angami community in particular and other tribal communities in general which get roll on to the generation through memory. Thus when Kire says "I wrote [*Mari*] in my head" she is also co-relating the technique of her narration to the tradition of the local history. The form of the history in *Mari* varies whereas the pattern of the tradition remains the same. In this sense; the text in its aesthetic actively vocals the local.

With the local history, the text of *Mari* gains significance from three points of view. Firstly, symbolically it gains momentum in appearing more as a natural tree, sprouting as a single aesthetic sapling and gradually wearing multiple branches and leaves of local histories, more is the growth firm is the grounding, more it embraces the fathomless sky the more local earth it holds and makes it stronger, gradually translating a part into whole enabling each other. In simple terms the text of *Mari* is a tree itself, it gradually translates into the nature, life and part of the local history. Secondly, the local spirituality and community sense that the text echoes are not different things of life in *Mari*, rather they are life itself. Fear for spirit and clan boundaries reverberate with a general concern- the community well being, an ethos of the tribal community. The local history in its real essence endorses peace, anything even though enchanting which negotiates the essence and if it is within the capacity of the community is virtually rejected. This is the reason why the Angami people rejected the offer of the Deputy Commissioner. Further, they fear that more mourning will infuriate their ancestors that may invoke their wrath for their community; they fear that breaking the clan boundaries may

disturb community balance and plunge it into war.

Thirdly, both the sentiments have a deep community concern, its safety, well being and unity for existence. This sense triggered by the text can confront some of the dominating western literary perspectives in vogue today. The message of the text becomes apparent. It tends to give a Marxist like message at first. But if this perspective is endorsed, the text of *Mari* once again will confront it as it does not substantiate it from a class struggle point of view in the tribal clans. The tribal community in fact does have class category as Marx claims in the European context. Significantly then, the community sense that *Mari* triggers from the history can be a priori to what Marx claims, 'a local model that can become a counter perspective to the colonial. If promoted, it can become a significant tool of enquiry in research which will be more binding, uniting and enabling unlike the Marxist model which begins and ends with division. Marx is more informed by slavery since early Greek and Roman ages that translated into Feudalism in terms of serfs and feudal lords in the Medieval Age and bourgeois and proletariats in the latest. Whereas a perspective that a text like *Mari* triggers has a very different context that cannot even dream of salve tradition, therefore it will be unique.

In continuation, the sense of unity the text explores that binds the tribal community into one whole and its practical possibility can hit back the claim of the poststructuralist thinking, particularly Derridean. Beginning linguistically and gradually ending with philosophy, echoing the view of Marx, Derrida hijacks the discourse theory in Michel Foucault which considers knowledge as contingencies. According to Perry Anderson, as quoted by Spivak in "Can the Subaltern Speak?," "With Derrida, the self-cancellation of structuralism latent in the

recourse to music or madness in Levi-Strauss or Foucault is consummated. With no commitment to exploration of social realities at all, Derrida had little compunction in undoing the constructions of these two, convicting them both of a 'nostalgia of origins'" (Spivak 87). Anderson thus concludes that Derrida does not recognize social realities, does not recognize language as discourse, and rather considers the origin as nostalgia.

This denial of origin in fact becomes the crux of the poststructuralist perspective which prevails over the higher academia. Denial of the origin implies fragmentation. In this sense, I would like to argue that the Derridean thought is much informed by the post-war fragmented psychology that considers the fragmentation, the rootlessness as the reality which in fact is the extension of the post-war catastrophe, the destruction, into human psychology. Therefore, it can be affirmed that the poststructuralist thought functions more as a whitewash to war crime than a reality. A context in which *Mari* like text springs neither has the war context (the war in the text is imposed upon, a foreign assault), nor the slavery, therefore any literary perspective deduced from it pertaining to the dominating perspective in reference will be local and thus unique. The originary sense of the Angami community, the community oriented perspective, therefore, is also a befitting reply to the tenets in the perspectives as in reference and by exploring and promoting them, Kire has tendered a very commendable service to the epistemological origin of the North East India that the generation must know.

Mari like texts will have a huge scope which has already been demonstrated by its success in reception across the globe. Tradition has shown that every literary production grounded on local history has taken epic dimension. Local history breathes the life of the *Iliad* and the *Odyssey* in

terms of the fall of Troy; the *Aeneid* recounts the origin of the history of the Roman Empire in terms of Aeneid; the *Paradise Lost* and the *Paradise Regain* reframe the divine history of the origin and the fall of human beings; the *Mahabharata* encompasses the history of the rise and fall of the Kuru Dynasty and the *Ramayana* the kingdom of Lanka.

The history that goes into the fabrics of the epic is contextual. *Mari* is not an epic but it senses its attributes in terms of the orality of the local history of the Angami Nagas, its fall from the offence of the war and rejuvenation in terms of the text and thus tends to become an epic for them. Artillery shelling of the village to its debris during the war and its renovation by the villagers is a symbolic fall and rise of the village. In this sense, it carries the attention of the readers beyond the stigma of the "conflict" zone and aligns itself with the great intellectual potentiality of the region that had contributed in part, for instance, in the formation of one of the greatest epics *Mahabharata*, unfortunately silenced long by the stigma triggered by the modern history. In Kire, seen from this angle, the history revives not simply with the materiality of the evidence, rather the evidence takes a metaphorical bent and spirals into the yet unfolded pages of the memory and thus changes its narration. It is this *historiopetics*, that is to say a frame that intertwines both the techniques of history and art, (re)generates both

the history and the literature in their essence in Kire.

Works Cited

- Anderson, Perry. *In the Tracks of Historical Materialism*. Verso, 1983.
- Gomez, A. Luis. "Myth and Ethos in Three Novels by Naga Write Easterine Kire." *National Herald*, www.nationalheraldindia.com/reviews-recommendations/a-tale-of-two-easterine-kires-myth-and-ethos-in-three-novels. Accessed 26 June 2020.
- Kire, Easterine. *Mari*. Harper Collins, 2010.
- Ray, Prajna Parimita. "Terror Tales: The Naga Insurgency in the Writings of Temsula Ao and Easterine Kire." *MJU Journal of Literature and Culture Studies*, vol. 3, no.1, June 2016, pp. 57-71.
- Sharma, Shiva Prasad. "Easterine Kire's Fictions and Nagaland." *Palarch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology*, vol. 17, no.7, 2020, pp. 10800-10810.
- Spivak, Gayatri Chakravrti. "Can the Subaltern Speak?" *Colonial Discourse and Post-colonial Theory*, edited by Patrick Williams and Laura Chrisman, Columbia UP, 1993, pp.66-111.

